

Probability of Default. A Machine Learning Approach for Non-Financial Companies

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Abstract:

This paper aims to enhance credit risk assessment for non-financial companies in Romania by developing a machine learning (ML) model to estimate the probability of default. Utilizing an extensive set of microeconomic data, including financial statements, loan-level data from the Credit Risk Register, shareholder structure, export and import activities, and external debt, the model provides a comprehensive analysis of a company's financial health and risk profile. The ML model employs logistic regression for classification, with 80% of the data used for training and 20% for validation. The

model's performance was evaluated using the receiver operating characteristic curve and confusion matrix, demonstrating an accuracy of 88%. Further validation through point-in-time estimation confirmed the model's stability. The study is limited by the relatively low number of defaulting companies in the sample and the unique economic disruptions of 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. To account for these factors, a Random Under Sample Boosted Trees approach is employed, which improves the model's ability to distinguish between defaulted and non-defaulted debtors. Despite these limitations, the research concludes that integrating extensive financial data and advanced ML techniques have the potential to markedly enhance credit risk assessment, providing a reliable tool for financial institutions to manage credit risk effectively. Future improvements could address data imbalance and incorporate more diverse economic conditions to enhance predictive power for defaulting companies.

Keywords: *credit risk, machine learning, microdata.*

Introduction

The proper assessment of risks associated with lending activities continues to be a central concern for regulatory authorities and credit institutions. Credit risk represents the probability that a borrower will fail to meet their financial obligations, causing losses to the creditor. In a globalized financial environment where companies, governments, and financial institutions are interconnected, adequate credit risk management is vital to preventing financial crises and ensuring long-term economic health. This is especially critical in a banking sector like

Romania's, which has a traditional business model focused on lending to non-financial companies and the population. A crucial aspect of credit risk management is the correct assessment of borrowers' repayment capacity. This paper proposes a machine learning (ML) model to determine the probability of default (PD) at the level of non-financial companies in Romania, using an extensive set of microeconomic information.

Literature Review

Credit risk remains a major vulnerability for banking systems worldwide. A study conducted by the Bank for International Settlements (2000) indicated that the most severe problems that credit institutions have encountered are often related to insufficient lending standards or inadequate assessments of borrowers' financial situations.

Traditionally, credit risk is defined as the possibility of suffering losses due to borrowers' failure to meet their financial obligations on the established dates (Winkler, 2008). In the European Union, the European Banking Authority (2024) reported a total of approximately 365 billion euros in non-performing loans, representing 1.84% of total loans, a higher percentage than in the United States (1.4%). In Romania, the percentage of non-performing loans was 2.4% at the end of 2023 (NBR, 2024), with the non-financial companies' sector substantially contributing to this figure. In March 2024, the percentage of non-performing loans for non-financial companies was 3.8%.

In this context, the accurate assessment of risks associated with lending activities has proven to be a major concern for regulatory authorities and credit institutions. In the literature, three main methodologies are delineated for modeling credit risk in the non-financial companies' sector:

- i) Linear models use a linear function based on the financial indicators of companies. A notable example is the model developed by Altman (1968), which is used to calculate the "Z-score".
- ii) Non-linear models, which include logit and probit models, assume that the PD follows a logistic or cumulative normal distribution. Ohlson (1980), one of the most well-known proponents of using logit models for credit risk assessment, identifies four decisive factors: company size, financing structure, performance, and liquidity.

Costeiu and Neagu (2013) developed a bottom-up logit model to estimate the PD for non-financial companies in Romania that accessed

loans from local banks, using the firms' financial indicators as explanatory variables. Subsequently, the authors integrated this model into a macroeconomic framework to analyze the impact of recent macroeconomic developments on the banking sector.

- iii) Non-linear, non-parametric models include neural networks or support vector machines.

The Bank of England (2022) identified several primary ML methods that financial institutions in the UK use: (i) Advanced regression techniques, such as ridge regression and Lasso, apply regularization to standard models, reducing the number of input variables and improving generalization; (ii) Tree-based models utilize decision trees for regression and classification tasks, often through ensemble methods that combine multiple decision trees; (iii) Neural networks, inspired by brain structures, consist of layers of interconnected nodes and are used for a variety of applications, including computer vision and natural language processing; (iv) Natural language processing employs algorithms to convert unstructured language data into a computable form; and (v) Dimensionality reduction techniques, including feature selection and feature extraction, reduce the number of variables by creating a smaller set of principal variables.

Apart from the choice of model, other elements of model design can significantly influence the results obtained and the banks' ability to manage risks. In designing a model, Engelmann and his colleagues (2006) emphasize the importance of defining the default event, choosing the time horizon for estimates, and determining the calibration method. Especially for logit models, it is essential to have a sufficient number of defaulting companies in the sample to obtain precise estimates.

The digitalization of processes and the integration of AI have become intrinsic to our daily lives, particularly since the COVID-19 pandemic. This trend has persisted with the rise of online loans, leading to higher uncertainty for financial institutions and, consequently, the necessity to develop new models to manage the

associated credit risk (Chen et al., 2020). One of the newly developed tools is the ML models.

ML algorithms utilize extensive datasets to identify patterns and generate insightful recommendations. As credit risk modeling benefits from vast and varied data, it is an ideal field for applying ML to enhance analytical value (Vidovic and Yue, 2020).

On one hand, ML models have the potential to identify subtle relationships and capture various nonlinearities while effectively processing unstructured data. Applications such as fraud detection and textual data analytics benefit from ML's ability to function without predefined structures or theoretical models with assumptions. Instead, the data empirically drives the ML model (Vidovic and Yue, 2020).

On the other hand, there are also several drawbacks to the use of such models. Noriega et al. (2023) review a series of papers that employ ML estimations and identify several limitations of this method that were encountered during experiments. A significant portion of studies exhibited a lack of representativeness of reality, where variables do not accurately reflect the true nature of information. Unbalanced data was another common issue that significantly reduced model performance. Inconsistencies in information recording, such as errors, bias, and noise, necessitate data cleaning, which risks information loss. The inability to explain results is a limitation in many robust ML models. Additionally, the need for centralized information processing can introduce losses, noise, and delays. Lastly, better adaptability in processing both structured and unstructured data is needed.

Materials and Methods

The ML model for estimating the PD is built on a comprehensive set of information, with the primary source being the financial statements of all companies operating in Romania. These financial indicators are essential as they provide critical insights into a company's financial health and stability. By analyzing elements such as revenue, expenses, assets, liabilities, and equity,

the model can assess the company's ability to meet its financial obligations.

In addition to the financial statements, the model incorporates loan-level data from the Credit Risk Register, which includes detailed information about the companies' borrowing history and their repayment performance. This data is important for understanding the companies' credit behaviors and identifying patterns that might indicate an increased risk of default. The dependent variable in this context is the default indicator, which signifies whether a company has payment delays that are greater than 90 days.

Moreover, the model leverages other databases that provide information on shareholder structure, which can influence a company's financial decisions and risk profile. Data on export and import activities are also included, as these activities reflect a company's operational scope and exposure to international markets, which can affect its risk profile. Additionally, information on external debt is considered, since high levels of external borrowing can increase financial vulnerability, especially in volatile economic conditions.

In total, the quantitative model is based on approximately 511,000 observations, spanning the period from 2016 to 2022, with data collected annually. This extensive dataset aims to ensure a robust analysis by capturing various economic cycles and trends over the years. Among these observations, 97.7% are non-defaults, indicating companies that have managed to meet their financial obligations, while 2.3% are defaults, representing companies that have failed to do so (Table 1).

The first step in estimating the ML model is the generation of the dataset, which undergoes a rigorous cleaning process. In the initial phase of cleaning, companies that have certain basic indicator values that are not coherent from an economic perspective, such as firms with negative turnover, or those with debts, equity, or total assets less than zero, are eliminated. Additionally, the following adjustment is applied to firms with losses and negative equity in the case of ROE: $(-1)*ROE$.

Table 1. Sample Distribution by Year and Default

Default	0	1	Total
2016	60,455	2,243	62,698
2017	64,610	1,940	66,550
2018	69,515	1,957	71,472
2019	71,711	1,700	73,411
2020	76,872	1,414	78,286
2021	75,546	1,222	76,768
2022	80,386	1,132	81,518
Total	499,095	11,608	510,703

Source: MoF, NBR, Author’s calculations

Next, the distributions of the indicators are reviewed to identify the presence of extreme values. Given the high level of polarization in the non-financial corporate sector in Romania, the initial values of the variables exhibit very wide distributions. To reduce the influence of these extreme values, the financial indicators undergo a winsorization process, setting a threshold of 10%.

The generated dataset encompasses the main categories for assessing the financial position of companies, targeting the firms’ ability to generate profit, their efficiency in using available resources, the structure of assets, the structure of liabilities and debt levels, their liquidity, as well as their growth rates from one period to another.

The paper employs a ML model to automatically classify debtors using the extensive set of indicators mentioned above. Classification is a type of supervised ML in which an algorithm “learns” to categorize new observations based on labeled data examples.

In this study, the dataset was divided into two samples: 80% was used for training and developing the model, while the remaining 20% was used to validate the results obtained from the development sample.

The classification technique used for the ML model was based on logistic regression.

$$\text{Logit}(P_{it}(Y_{i,t} = 1|x_1, x_2 \dots x_n)) = \alpha_i + \beta_i \text{financial indicators}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Given that the literature (Alam et al., 2020; Song and Peng, 2019; de Castro Vieira et al., 2019; Mitra et al., 2022) indicates that in the case of ML models, the existence of an unbalanced sample across classes (i.e., default vs. non-default) can generate a bias towards the predominant event, a new estimation of the ML model is performed, this time using the Random Under Sample (RUS) Boosted Trees technique, which takes this data characteristic into account.

The performance of the ML model was evaluated using the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve and the confusion matrix. Additionally, the stability of the ML model was tested using both through-the-cycle and point-in-time perspectives by running the model on annual data for the obtained specification.

Results and Discussion

The ML model designed to estimate the PD is founded on an extensive and detailed set of information, relying in its estimation on approximately 106 financial ratios built from the financial statements of all Romanian companies that had a bank loan during the period 2016–2022.

Figure 1. ROC for the Through the Cycle ML Model Estimation

Source: Author’s calculations

The financial ratios tested in the model cover a broad range of indicators. The dataset includes key categories for evaluating a company's financial position. It assesses profitability, resource efficiency, asset and liability structure, debt levels, liquidity, and growth rates over time.

The through-the-cycle model, which incorporates data spanning the entire period, demonstrates a strong ability to distinguish between defaulters and non-defaulters. The model's accuracy ratio is at 88% (Figure 1), indicating a high level of precision in its predictions.

The results achieved using the through-the-cycle approach are further validated by conducting a point-in-time estimation with the ML classifier. This step is important to evaluate the model's performance stability over time. According to the figures presented in Table 2, the accuracy ratio of the model fluctuates between 86% and 89% during the period from 2016 to 2022.

Table 2. ROC Evolution for Point-in-Time Machine Learning Model Estimation

	ROC
2016	86%
2017	86%
2018	86%
2019	87%
2020	86%
2021	87%
2022	89%

Source: author's calculations

However, an examination of the confusion matrix (Figure 2), which provides a detailed analysis of the model's performance in distinguishing between defaulted and non-defaulted debtors, reveals a notable discrepancy. The ML model demonstrates greater accuracy in classifying companies that do not have payment delays exceeding 90 days, meaning those that are not in default, compared to its ability to identify defaulting companies.

One possible reason for this discrepancy could be the relatively low number of defaulting companies in the sample over the analyzed period, which presents a limitation for this study. This imbalance in the dataset likely hampers the

model's ability to learn and accurately predict defaults. Additionally, another limitation is the fact that the only year with significant negative economic developments within the sample is 2020. The economic disruptions during this year were primarily due to measures implemented to contain the COVID-19 pandemic, rather than to typical fluctuations in the business cycle. This unique scenario may not contribute to a characteristic representation of economic downturns, further affecting the model's ability to generalize across different economic conditions.

Figure 2. Confusion Matrix for the Through the Cycle ML Model Estimation

Source: Author's calculations

These factors collectively suggest that while the model is effective in certain aspects, there is room for improvement with regard to enhancing its predictive power for defaulting companies. To account for this weakness, the RUS Boosted Trees technique was used, which balances the data by randomly under-sampling the classes with more members. RUS Boost is an efficient method for managing imbalances in training data, thereby contributing to more accurate classification. Thus, for each of the k classes, a data subset with n observations per class is formed, improving the classification accuracy for all classes, including the minority ones.

Figure 3. Confusion Matrix for the RUS Boost ML Model Estimation

Source: Author's calculations

The overall performance of the revised model remains stable, but more importantly, there is a significant improvement in its ability to correctly classify companies that enter default. The confusion matrix finally indicates an accuracy of approximately 80% for both categories of debtors.

Conclusion

The comprehensive assessment of credit risk is essential for maintaining the stability of financial institutions and the broader economy, particularly in a globalized environment where the interconnectedness of companies, governments, and financial entities can lead to significant systemic risk. This paper presents a ML model designed to estimate the PD for non-financial companies in Romania by utilizing an extensive set of microeconomic data. The primary data source includes the financial statements of these companies, supplemented by detailed loan-level data from the Credit Risk Register, shareholder structure information, export and import activities, and external debt data.

The integration of these diverse data sources allows the model to capture an exhaustive view of each company's financial health and risk profile. The financial indicators used in the model provide crucial insights into profitability,

resource efficiency, asset and liability structure, debt levels, liquidity, and growth rates, which are critical for assessing a company's ability to meet its financial obligations.

The ML model employs a logistic regression-based classification technique to distinguish between defaulters and non-defaulters. The dataset was divided into two samples: 80% for training and developing the model, and 20% for validating the results. The model's performance was evaluated using the ROC curve and the confusion matrix. The through-the-cycle approach demonstrated an accuracy ratio of 88%, demonstrating high precision in its predictions.

Further validation through point-in-time estimation revealed that the model's accuracy ratio ranged between 86% and 89% from 2016 to 2022, underscoring its stability and reliability over different economic conditions. However, the analysis also highlighted some limitations. The relatively low number of defaulting companies in the sample and the unique economic disruptions of 2020, primarily driven by the COVID-19 pandemic, may affect the model's ability to generalize across different economic scenarios. To address this issue, the RUS Boosted Trees ML method was used. This technique enhances the classification accuracy for all classes, including those that make up a small proportion, and contributes to a more accurate classification overall. While the comprehensive performance of the revised model remains stable, a significant improvement occurred in correctly classifying companies that enter default, with the confusion matrix indicating an accuracy of about 80% for both categories of debtors.

In conclusion, while the machine learning model shows robust performance in classifying debtors and provides valuable insights into credit risk management, there is potential for further enhancement. Further addressing the data imbalance and incorporating more diverse economic conditions could improve the model's predictive power for defaulting companies. Overall, this study underscores the importance of integrating extensive financial data and

advanced machine learning techniques in developing reliable tools for credit risk assessment.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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